

FEATURES OF CHANGES IN THE CONCENTRATION OF PRO-INFLAMMATORY CYTOKINES IN NEWBORN CHILDREN WITH INTRAUTERINE GROWTH RETARDATION

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Abstract. An important informative indicator of the immune system status of newborns during the adaptation period is the level of cytokine production. Objective of the study is to investigate the characteristics of changes in the concentration of pro-inflammatory cytokines in the serum of newborns with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). The immunological examination was conducted on 122 newborns. All newborns were divided into three groups: the main group consisted of 58 children with IUGR who were born asphyxiated, the comparison group included 45 newborns with IUGR who were born without signs of asphyxia, and the control group comprised 19 practically healthy newborns. In children with IUGR, especially those born asphyxiated, there is a significant imbalance in the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (*IL-1 β* and *IL-8* increased by 2.6 and 3.6 times, respectively; *IFN- γ* decreased by 1.5 times). The most pronounced changes were observed in newborns with the symmetric variant of IUGR.

Keywords: intrauterine growth restriction, newborn, cytokines, pro-inflammatory cytokines.

In the structure of perinatal pathology, the conditions of newborns associated with chronic intrauterine hypoxia occupy a central place, leading to disruptions in adaptation processes during the neonatal period, damage to the central nervous system in 25-97% of children, and accompanied by intrauterine growth retardation (IUGR) [1,7,8].

According to WHO experts, the frequency of IUGR in Central Asia reaches 31.1%, in the USA — 10-15%, in Russia — 2.4-17%. In Europe, the frequency of low-birth-weight infants ranges from 3.0% (Iceland) to 8.8% (Cyprus). The frequency of IUGR increases with decreasing gestational age. Thus, at 41 weeks and above, the frequency is 5.7%, at 37-40 weeks - 5.5%, at 34-36 weeks - 7.4%. At 31-33 weeks - 9.4%, at 28-30 weeks - 13.1% [5,9].

Chronic intrauterine hypoxia, which plays one of the main roles in the pathogenesis of IUGR, causes early activation of the fetal immune system with subsequent dysfunction, sometimes leading to the development of secondary immunodeficiency, which results in infectious complications in these children [2]. Prolonged oxygen deprivation leads to disruption of immune regulation, which also contributes to a range of diseases in children with IUGR in the postnatal period [4,10].

An important informative indicator of the immune system status of newborns during the adaptation period is the level of cytokine production, which serves as a link between immunity, hemostasis, hematopoiesis, angiopoiesis, and nonspecific resistance of the body, acting as regulators of all major life processes [3]. Cytokines are universal regulatory proteins designed to control the processes of proliferation, differentiation, apoptosis, and functional activity of cellular elements in hematopoietic, immune, and other systems of the body. Immunological mechanisms

in the pathogenesis of IUGR are dominant, and their pathological development largely characterizes the diversity of clinical manifestations in IUGR [6].

The study of the level of production of pro-inflammatory cytokines is of significant importance for assessing the immune status, including the cytokine profile in newborns with IUGR, as they facilitate intercellular regulation of body functions.

Objective of the study: To identify the features of changes in the concentration of pro-inflammatory cytokines in the serum of newborn children with intrauterine growth retardation.

Materials and methods of the study: During the study, immunological examination was conducted on 122 newborns. All newborns were divided into 3 groups: the main group consisted of 58 children with intrauterine growth retardation born in asphyxia, the comparison group consisted of 45 newborns with intrauterine growth retardation born without signs of asphyxia, and the control group consisted of 19 practically healthy newborns.

The levels of IL-1 β , IL-8, and IFN- γ were determined using the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) method with commercial reagent kits from Vector-Best LLC (Russia, Novosibirsk) at the Institute of Immunology and Human Genome of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Statistical processing of the obtained data was performed using the Statistics 6.0 software. The significance of differences in the mean values of the compared indicators was assessed using the Student's t-test (t).

Results of the study: The pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-1 β plays an important physiological role in immune regulation processes, initiating inflammation and sometimes being a key link in the pathogenesis of many diseases, including immune-mediated ones. Disruption of the cytokine balance towards hyperproduction of IL-1 β may be a central link in the pathogenesis of many known chronic diseases.

We conducted a study to determine the level of IL-1 β production as an important mediator, which is one of the most universal regulators of immunity and inflammatory reactions with a wide range of biological effects, including the proliferation of T and B lymphocytes, antibody formation, and the induction of the synthesis of other cytokines. It was established that in healthy newborns, individual levels of IL-1 β production ranged from 140 to 260 pg/ml, with an average value of this cytokine being 200.56 ± 28 pg/ml. In newborns with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) who were born in asphyxia, the level of the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-1 β before treatment in peripheral blood was 514.86 ± 05 pg/ml, remaining significantly high ($P < 0.001$) compared to control values, and was 1.2 times higher than in children with IUGR born without asphyxia (Table 1).

The high level of IL-1 β production in newborns with IUGR suggests a certain dependence of its concentration on the nature of the pathological process, as evidenced by its increase in newborns with IUGR born in asphyxia.

Table 1.

Level of cytokine concentration in newborns with IUGR in observation groups (pg/ml)

Indicators pg/ml	Control (n=19)	Main group (n=58)	Comparison group (n=45)	P
IL-1 β	200,5 \pm 6,28	514,8 \pm 6,05	417,4 \pm 4,08	P<0,001
IL-8	188,4 \pm 11,30	671,7 \pm 10,97	528,6 \pm 10,25	P<0,001
IFN- γ	25,7 \pm 1,56	17,0 \pm 0,65	16,3 \pm 0,62	P<0,001

IL-8 is the earliest pro-inflammatory cytokine, a protein that belongs to chemokines and is a powerful chemotactic and activating factor for neutrophils. The main function of IL-8 is to act as a chemoattractant for neutrophils, macrophages, lymphocytes, and eosinophils. In newborns with IUGR born in asphyxia, the concentration of IL-8 was significantly (3.6 times) increased to 671.7 ± 10.97 pg/ml compared to the control group of 188.4 ± 11.30 pg/ml. A comparative analysis of IL-8 production among children in the main group and the comparison group showed that in children with IUGR born in asphyxia, the concentration of IL-8 was 1.3 times higher (671.7 ± 10.91 pg/ml) than in newborns with IUGR born without asphyxia (528.6 ± 10.25 pg/ml) (Table 1).

Interferons play an important role in coordinating the functional connectivity of the multi-component immune system. They are a group of biologically active proteins or glycoproteins synthesized by cells in response to foreign antigens. It is known that one of the important mediators for characterizing the state of the immune system in patients is IFN- γ , which regulates the intensity of the immune response, increasing the bactericidal activity of phagocytic cells, and possesses antiviral and immunomodulatory activity.

The interferon system is aimed at recognizing and eliminating foreign genetic information. An important function of IFN- γ is its participation in establishing connections between lymphocytes and macrophages, as well as in regulating cellular and humoral immune responses. In our studies, the level of IFN- γ production in healthy newborns averaged 25.71 ± 56 pg/ml (Table 1).

For newborns in the main and comparison groups, a reduced production of IFN- γ was characteristic, being 1.5 times lower compared to the control group, which amounted to 17.00 ± 65 pg/ml and 16.30 ± 62 pg/ml respectively ($P < 0.001$). This further reflects the degree of immune system dysfunction in IUGR. The concentration of IFN- γ among children in the main group and the comparison group did not have significant differences. The low ability of newborns to synthesize IFN- γ leads to a disturbance in the immunoregulatory index towards the predominance of suppressor activity of T-lymphocytes and a decrease in the killer activity of cells.

We also analyzed the cytokine profile in newborns with IUGR in the studied groups depending on the clinical variant (Table 2).

Table 2.

The state of the cytokine profile in newborns with IUGR depending on the clinical variant (pg/ml)

Indicators pg/ml	Main group		Comparison group	
	symmetrical variant n-32	asymmetrical variant n-26	symmetrical variant n-20	asymmetrical variant n-25
IL-1 β	525,5 \pm 8,8* [^]	501,5 \pm 6,9	425,1 \pm 7,7	411,3 \pm 7,0
IL-8	699,2 \pm 13,1* [^]	637,8 \pm 15,7 [^]	566,6 \pm 17*	506,2 \pm 17,1
IFN- γ	17,0 \pm 0,9	17,0 \pm 0,8	16,1 \pm 1,0	16,44 \pm 1,1

Note: *- the difference between the variants of IUGR within groups $P < 0.001$. [^]- the difference between the variants of IUGR between groups $P < 0.001$. As can be seen from the presented data, in newborns of the main group with a symmetric variant of IUGR, the concentration of the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-1 β (525.5 ± 8.8 pg/ml) was

significantly higher ($P < 0.001$) than in newborns with an asymmetric variant of IUGR (501.5 ± 6.9 pg/ml).

In the comparison group, no significant differences between the variants were observed. A significant difference was also found between the cytokine IL-1 β levels in newborns with the symmetric variant of IUGR in the main group (525.5 ± 8.8 pg/ml) and the symmetric variant of the comparison group (425.1 ± 7.7 pg/ml), as well as with the asymmetric variant of the main group (501.5 ± 6.9 pg/ml) and the asymmetric variant of the comparison group (411.3 ± 7.0 pg/ml).

The levels of the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-8 showed significant ($P < 0.001$) differences between the symmetric and asymmetric variants of IUGR, 699.2 ± 13.1 pg/ml and 637.8 ± 15.7 pg/ml in the main group and in the comparison group, respectively 566.6 ± 17 pg/ml and 506.2 ± 17.1 pg/ml. It was established that the level of IL-8 in newborns with the symmetric variant of IUGR in the main group (699.2 ± 13.1 pg/ml) is significantly higher than in children of the same variant in the comparison group (566.6 ± 17.7 pg/ml). In children with the asymmetric variant of IUGR in the main group, this indicator is significantly higher than in newborns with the asymmetric variant in the comparison group.

Conclusions: thus, our studies have shown that in children with IUGR, especially those born in asphyxia, there is a significant imbalance in the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-8 increase by 2.6; 3.6 times, IFN- γ decreases by 1.5 times). The most pronounced changes were found in newborns with the symmetric variant of IUGR.

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